

A Reproducibility Study of Detecting Cyberbullying Across Different Social Media Platforms Using Deep Learning

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ABSTRACT

Cyberbullying is a serious issue in social media. Every day, people produce a huge amount of content over different platforms. Sometimes, it is offensive and aims at hurting others. There are already some mechanisms to report and cope with this phenomenon; however, most are ineffective. Therefore, the topic is analysed in the existing literature. Some approaches use traditional Machine Learning methods, but their performance is not satisfactory. In recent studies, Deep Learning models are examined and are claimed to have superior results. In this paper, we reproduced a study that used Deep Neural Network models for classifying offensive content. We compared its performance to the traditional machine learning models. We were able to reconduct the experiments; nevertheless, we observed that the experimental setup used in the study had some flaws. It led to overly optimistic results. We point out the limitations of the current setup and compare our results with the reported ones.

Author Keywords

Deep Learning, Reproducibility Study, Cyberbullying

INTRODUCTION

Over the past years, there is a constant increase in the usage of the Internet and mobile phones. In many fields it has a great impact, it provides quick access to information, allows people to connect and discuss their ideas easily. However, it also creates many threats. One of the areas most vulnerable to them is social media, news websites and other tools that incorporate a possibility to interact between users. A huge amount of messages, posts and articles are created every day. Most of them contain interesting and useful content; however, some are created with the intent to embarrass or hurt other people. This phenomenon is called cyberbullying. Most adolescents use some kind of social media nowadays [6]. The research of [10] shows that between 20% and 40% teenagers have experienced cyberbullying at least once in their lives. Moreover, social media have a big impact to create and influence opinions. Therefore, it is important to create tools that could allow filtering harmful content from the web.

On the big social media platforms, there are already some mechanisms that allow users to report offensive behaviours. Those reports are then manually analysed and filtered. However, with the increasing number of posts and communication, this approach is not feasible and an automatic way of cyberbullying detection is needed. A lot of research is being carried out on this issue but there is no perfect solution yet. The topic is complicated and there are many challenges to overcome. Many posts and messages are anonymous, their interpretation depends on the context and the whole classification is subjective. Moreover, types of language and harmful words differ across the platforms, so it is difficult to create a model that generalizes well across them.

In this paper, we focused on reproducing the results from [1] where Deep Neural Network (DNN) models were used to classify toxic messages across 3 different social media platforms. Based on their results, Deep Learning significantly outperforms traditional Machine Learning (ML) approaches. The paper reports high F1 scores (over 90% for some datasets). However, we came to the conclusion that these values were not accurate. The authors have provided source code which we ran and compare our outcomes with their results.

We started with reproducing their evaluation of traditional ML models. During the work on the code, we discovered that there was an error, which led to a mistake in the reporting of the results. Moreover, the authors did employ any hyperparameter tuning. This raises the question whether traditional ML could obtain a better performance than reported. The second step was to reproduce the results for DNN models. In this case, we found another bug in the code. Oversampling was used, in order to offset the class imbalance between offensive and non-offensive posts. The oversampling was done on the entire data set, before dividing the model into training and testing data. This led to data leakage. After correcting the error, we were able to show that the model is not as accurate as reported when it comes to generalization on the unseen data. The performance dropped from over 90% to about 80%. Nevertheless, we ran their models and were able to reproduce some of the results.

In the next section, we make a summary of other papers that focused on reproducing [1]. Afterwards, we describe the experimental setup and the models that were used in the study. Then, we focus on the results for both traditional ML and DNN models and we point out limitations of the current setup. In the end, we provide a description of the significance testing that we performed and conclusions.

OTHER REPRODUCIBILITY STUDIES

We found 3 other studies that also aimed at reproducing [1]. In [3], they reproduced the paper without any changes in the source code. Their results were pretty similar to the original paper. They did not indicate the error with traditional ML code and oversampling. Also, they tried out how the methodology from the original paper works on a different dataset (Youtube dataset created by [4]). However, the error with oversampling might make the result overly positive (described more precisely in the next sections). In the other two papers, [2] and [5], that also reproduced [1], the error with oversampling was indicated and criticized. The authors have argued and proved that after correcting the error, models are not able to generalize that well. Moreover, they indicated that the datasets used have some flaws. They tried out enriching the dataset with more data which led to much better results.

REPRODUCED EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Datasets

Our goal was to reproduce the experiments carried out in [1]. First of all, we analysed how the data was collected and how it is structured. In the study, three different public datasets were used. They contain posts from different online platforms marked either as offensive or neutral. All of them were anonymized and manually annotated. However, there is one main issue with them. Classes are highly imbalanced. There are significantly more neutral posts than those marked as bullying. In order to overcome this issue, oversampling of the minority class was done. Also, the length of some posts is much higher than the average. Thus, very long posts were truncated in preprocessing to match the length of the post ranked at 95 percentile in the dataset.

Each dataset was collected on a different platform and has slightly different characteristics.

- Formspring [8]: It was a question-and-answer based website where users could ask and answer questions from other users. The dataset consists of 12000 question and answer tuples annotated as neutral or cyberbullying by three people. 825 of them were labelled as cyberbullying by at least two.
- Twitter [11]: It is a micro-blogging website where users can create posts and react to them with short messages called "tweets". Among 16000 tweets from the platform, 3117 are annotated as sexist and 1837 as racist. As pointed out in [2], this dataset has a potential bias. Racist tweets are generated by only 8 users and more than 90% of them were produced by a single user. Therefore, the algorithm might not work well for other users.
- Wikipedia [12]: It is a collaborative knowledge repository. The dataset consists of the posts from discussions of users who edited a particular page. It has in total 100000 entries, 13590 of which were annotated as a personal attack.

Setup of the Environment

The source code used in the study was available on GitHub. Therefore, we only needed to set up the environment to run in.

We had to use Python 2.7 environment because packages had incompatibilities with Python 3.x. As we could not get the information which packages versions were used in the original study, we had to figure out the package versions for ourselves. We picked the most recent package versions, with the constraint that the code would have to run without any errors in its default state. After initial research, we discovered that it is not possible to run the DNN models on Windows because of the unavailability of some packages for this operating system (for example Tensorflow 1.13.x). We therefore used a Linux environment and were able to determine a set of package versions that made the code executable. There are now two ways of running the code. Either via an anaconda environment or in a docker container. If further work on reproducibility will be done on this paper, we suggest downloading the docker container from dockerhub¹.

Methodology and Models

The original study consisted of two parts. First of all, traditional Machine Learning models were evaluated. F1 score was calculated for Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and Naive Bayes (NB) models. They were also evaluated for two text feature extraction methods: character n-gram and word unigram. These simple methods are used because it was shown in the past that they are better for detecting abusive language [1]. Hyper-parameter tuning was not performed.

In the second part, the study focuses on DNN models. Four different models were explored: Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Bidirectional LSTM (BLSTM) and BLSTM with attention (BLSTM a.). Each network consisted of the following sequence of 7 layers: Input, Embedding, first Dropout, Neural Architecture, second Dropout, Fully Connected and a final Softmax layer. Every layer, apart from the Neural Architecture, is the same for all DNN models.

Each layer has its particular function. The embedding layer is responsible for processing a fixed-size sequence of words. In the study, they tried out 3 different words embedding initialization: random, GloVe [7], and SSWE [9]. Then, during training, the model uses them to learn word embeddings for a particular task. It allows the model to capture the task-specific style of input. To reduce overfitting, two dropout layers with rates of 0.25 and 0.5 are used. The fully connected layer is a dense output layer with the number of neurons equal to the number of classes. The last step in the workflow is a softmax layer providing a softmax activation. Backpropagation with Adam optimizer was used to train the models. Categorical cross-entropy was used as the loss function.

RESULTS AND SETUP LIMITATIONS

Traditional Machine Learning

First of all, we ran traditional Machine Learning models using the source code from the original study. 10 fold cross-validation was used as the evaluation method. The obtained F1 scores can be seen in table Table 1. The scores were quite

¹<https://hub.docker.com/r/paulerpenstein/cyberbullying>

Dataset	Label	Character n-grams				Word unigrams			
		LR	SVM	RF	NB	LR	SVM	RF	NB
Formspring	Bully	0.50	0.48	0.27	0.03	0.49	0.46	0.26	0.03
Twitter	Racism	0.76	0.76	0.73	0.63	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.64
	Sexism	0.72	0.76	0.69	0.61	0.74	0.77	0.74	0.62
Wiki	Attack	0.70	0.69	0.68	0.67	0.71	0.69	0.73	0.66

Table 1. Performance of the traditional Machine Learning models measured by F1 score.

Dataset	Label	Precision			Recall			F1 score		
		Random	Glove	SSWE	Random	Glove	SSWE	Random	Glove	SSWE
F	Bully	0,39	0,46	-	0,31	0,43	-	0,34	0,43	-
F+	Bully	0,29	0,39	-	0,32	0,40	-	0,31	0,39	-
T	Racism	0,70	0,77	-	0,69	0,73	-	0,69	0,75	-
T+	Racism	0,65	0,72	-	0,69	0,78	-	0,67	0,75	-
T	Sexism	0,71	0,72	-	0,63	0,71	-	0,66	0,71	-
T+	Sexism	0,65	0,70	-	0,62	0,70	-	0,63	0,70	-
W	Attack	0,76	0,74	-	0,67	0,71	-	0,71	0,72	-
W+	Attack	0,67	0,72	-	0,62	0,70	-	0,65	0,71	-

Table 2. Comparison of the performance of BLSTM with attention model for different initial word embeddings using Precision, Recall and F1 score.

similar for some datasets and methods to those in [1]. However, some differed a lot.

During analysis of the source code, we found an error in the traditional Machine Learning models. Performance scores for multi-class classification in the Twitter dataset are output in the wrong order. In the method `get_scores`, the functions `precision_score`, `recall_score` and `f1_score` are returning values of the corresponding error measure for each class. However, they do it in a different order than is expected in the code. For each model other than the Twitter dataset, error measures are correct. It means that the results in table 3 of the original paper for traditional models are placed in wrong cells of the table. The correct F1 score for racism class should be F1 score for "no bullying" class, F1 score for sexism class should be F1 score for the racism class. When we fixed the order of the returned values to correspond to the expected ones (we did it using the "labels" parameter of the functions), the order of error measures for the Twitter dataset has changed. In the results section, we present the results for the corrected code. This situation shows, that open access to the source code is very important to enable cross-checks by reproducibility studies.

After correcting the error, our F1 scores for word unigrams were almost identical to those in Table 3 of [1]. However, for character n-grams, some differed slightly but the difference was in the range of standard error of the result. Dissimilarity might be caused by the fact that we did not know the exact version of packages that they use and a different operating system.

The next section will focus on comparing these results with the performance of DNN models. In our opinion, this comparison is not fully fair. For traditional models, there is no hyperparameter tuning or oversampling to reduce the class

imbalance (as they did for DNN). The authors of the original paper did not give traditional models a fair chance.

Deep Neural Networks

The next step was to run the four DNN models on different settings and evaluate their performance. Two main model optimisation techniques were explored: oversampling of the minority class and different initial word embeddings. The results of our investigations and experiments are described in detail in the next subsections.

All the models were implemented using the Keras library. Datasets were preprocessed in a standard way. Stop words and punctuation marks were removed and words were transformed to lower case. As in the original study the hold-out method with a test size of 0.1 was used as the evaluation method. We tried to use the same code as they did originally; however, due to the methodological error with oversampling, we had to make small changes (more details on that issue are in the next subsection). However, we only changed the place where oversampling is done, so the models themselves (and their hyperparameters), preprocessing and initial word embeddings were unaltered. Our code is available at: <https://github.com/PaulErpen/Detecting-Cyberbullying-Across-SMPs>.

In the result tables, the following abbreviations were used: – Datasets: F (Formspring), T (Twitter), W (Wikipedia) – Datasets with oversampling of bullying posts: F+ (Formspring), T+ (Twitter), W+ (Wikipedia) – Models: Convolutional CNN (Neural Network), LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory), BLSTM (Bidirectional LSTM), BLSTM a. (BLSTM with attention)

Dataset	Label	Random		Glove		SSWE	
		CNN	BLSTM a.	CNN	BLSTM a.	CNN	BLSTM a.
F	Bully	0,28	0,34	0,29	0,43	-	-
F+	Bully	0,43	0,31	0,40	0,39	-	-
T	Racism	0,72	0,69	0,65	0,75	-	-
T+	Racism	0,73	0,67	0,73	0,75	-	-
T	Sexism	0,59	0,66	0,55	0,71	-	-
T+	Sexism	0,64	0,63	0,64	0,70	-	-
W	Attack	0,68	0,71	0,69	0,72	-	-
W+	Attack	0,72	0,65	0,72	0,71	-	-

Table 3. Comparison of different word embeddings across CNN and BLSTM with attention models. F1 score was used as the performance measure.

Dataset	Label	Random		Glove		SSWE	
		CNN	BLSTM a.	CNN	BLSTM a.	CNN	BLSTM a.
F	Bully	-0,02	-0,10	+0,05	-0,18	-	-
F+	Bully	-0,48	-0,59	-0,53	-0,51	-	-
T	Racism	+0,04	-0,01	-0,10	-0,01	-	-
T+	Racism	-0,17	-0,29	-0,22	-0,18	-	-
T	Sexism	0,00	+0,01	-0,06	+0,06	-	-
T+	Sexism	-0,29	-0,30	-0,29	-0,21	-	-
W	Attack	-0,04	-0,05	-0,03	-0,02	-	-
W+	Attack	-0,11	-0,23	-0,17	-0,17	-	-

Table 4. Comparison of different word embeddings across CNN and BLSTM with attention models. F1 score was used as the performance measure. Values indicate the difference between our result and the corresponding value in the original dataset. If the value is positive, it means that our model performed better.

Effect of Oversampling

As mentioned before, all datasets have a problem of class imbalance. It biases the model to classify posts as non-bullying. In the original paper, they oversampled the minority class thrice to overcome this issue. However, they did it before splitting the data into training and test sets. This approach is wrong, as oversampling should be always done after splitting to avoid data leakage. If it is done before splitting, as they did in the paper, many samples from the test set appear also in the training set. It leads to significant overfitting and performance measures calculated on the test set are much better than they should be, because many points from the test set were used for model training.

Therefore, we decided to change their code and move oversampling after the holdout split. After making this change, we followed the procedure that was proposed in the original paper. We compared how well does the BLSTM with attention model perform with different initial word embeddings on both unaltered and oversampled datasets. The obtained performance measures can be seen in Table 2. We could not carry out the experiments for SSWE embeddings because they were not available (404 Not Found error). We tried to contact the authors of the paper, but with no success.

For unaltered datasets, our results were slightly different from the original ones, but the difference was not that big. Again it might be caused by different libraries versions or different operating system. However, in our results, for the oversampled

datasets performance metrics are much worse. It is caused by the fact that they overfit their data by wrong oversampling methodology. When done correctly, we could observe that oversampling did not help to improve the performance measures, and in most of the cases, it even made them worse. Therefore, the model is not able to generalize that well. Another insight is that Glove initial embedding performs better than Random one.

After analysing the results, we can say that oversampling did not solve the class imbalance problem. We have a hypothesis that class imbalance might be solved by enriching the dataset by bullying instances from other datasets. However, we did not check that idea.

Effect of Initial Word Embeddings

The next step was to compare different word embeddings across different models. Again we were not able to run them for SSWE word embeddings. As in the original paper, we tried 2 models: CNN and BLSTM with attention. The obtained F1 scores can be seen in Table 3. Again, we compared our results with the original ones. In Table 4 the differences between our result and the corresponding value in the original dataset were calculated. Our results are slightly different than in the original for the unaltered dataset (generally most of our values are slightly lower). For oversampled datasets, we got much lower performance, but it is expected, as we corrected data leakage.

Dataset	Label	Precision				Recall				F1 score			
		CNN	LSTM	BLSTM	BLSTM a.	CNN	LSTM	BLSTM	BLSTM a.	CNN	LSTM	BLSTM	BLSTM a.
F+	Bully	0,42	1,00	0,42	0,39	0,38	0,02	0,47	0,40	0,40	0,03	0,44	0,39
T+	Racism	0,72	0,72	0,75	0,72	0,73	0,80	0,77	0,78	0,73	0,76	0,76	0,75
	Sexism	0,77	0,65	0,66	0,70	0,55	0,77	0,71	0,70	0,64	0,70	0,68	0,70
W+	Attack	0,81	0,72	0,74	0,72	0,65	0,75	0,71	0,71	0,72	0,73	0,72	0,71

Table 5. Performance comparison of four DNN models with Glove initial word embedding. F1 score was used as the performance measure.

In our results, it can be observed that oversampling generally improves the performance of CNN. However, it does not change or even worsens BLSTM with attention. Glove embedding is much better for BLSTM, for CNN it is comparable with the Random one. Generally, for not oversampled datasets, we arrived at the same numbers as in the original paper.

Afterwards, we compared the performance of the four DNN models for precision, recall and F1 score with Glove initial word embedding for oversampled datasets (Table 5). As in previous points, we obtained much worse values. Also, in our case, all the models perform similarly, which contradicts the statement from the paper that the LSTM model is significantly worse.

Effect of the Data Distribution

There are two issues with the used datasets. Firstly, there is a class imbalance which was analysed in previous sections. The second problem is that for the Twitter dataset, most of the bullying instances come from a small group of users. It means that it might create a bias that the algorithm learns more about how to recognise particular users, not the cyberbullying itself. Also, because of it, the model performance might be overestimated. In [2], they tackled this issue. They enriched the dataset with entries from different datasets. It improved the model’s ability to generalize. However, many datasets can be biased in that way, so one should be very careful while designing algorithms for them.

SIGNIFICANCE TESTING

Model evaluation done only by comparing metrics can be misleading. Stating conclusions which model is better, especially if metrics are similar, might be statistically wrong. Therefore, we perform significance testing in order to compare the models.

McNemar’s test was used as it is suitable for deep learning models that take a long time to train. It is a recommended test for those situations as it only is based on predictions from fitted models.

We only use the best performing model from each of the categories of traditional machine learning and DNNs. Two sets of testing were done with statistical significance threshold of 0.05:

1. Comparing traditional machine learning models and deep learning models.

Null hypothesis: There is no significant difference between traditional machine learning model and deep learning model.

For ML models the best ones are SVM for Twitter, LR for Formspring, Random Forest for Wikipedia, all of them trained on Word unigrams. For the DNNs without oversampling BLSTM with attention performed best with Glove initial embeddings for all of the datasets.

	Twitter	Formspring	Wikipedia
Chi-squared	827.89	14.32	4.221
p-value	4.66e−182	1.53e−04	3.99e−02
Null hypothesis	<i>Rejected</i>	<i>Rejected</i>	<i>Rejected</i>

Table 6. Significance testing results on traditional machine learning models vs deep learning models.

Table 6 shows that there is a difference between ML models and DNN models, as the null hypothesis for every dataset was rejected. However when we look at metrics in Table 1 and Table 3 for corresponding models it can be noticed that for DNN models F1 scores are actually lower. Therefore we can’t confidently conclude that DNN models perform better.

2. Comparing DNN models with and without oversampled training data.

Null hypothesis: There is no significant difference between DNN models with and without oversampled training data.

Best DNN models with oversampling were again BLSTM with attention with Glove initial embeddings for all the datasets.

	Twitter	Formspring	Wikipedia
Chi-squared	0.53	3.70	29.158
p-value	4.67e−01	5.43e−02	6.67e−08
Null hypothesis	<i>Not rejected</i>	<i>Not rejected</i>	<i>Rejected</i>

Table 7. Significance testing results on deep learning models vs deep learning models with oversampled data.

The test in Table 7 shows that there is no significant difference for Formspring and Twitter models. For the Wikipedia data the results are significantly different than to the best performing DNN model. Similarly to previous experiment, when we look at metrics in Table 3 for corresponding models it can be noticed that for oversampled DNN model F1 score is

lower. Therefore we can't confidently conclude that oversampled DNN models perform better.

CONCLUSIONS

In the study, we reproduced a novel approach for the detection of cyberbullying across three different social media platforms. The approach compared traditional machine learning models and the DNN approach for solving the problem. The code for conducting the experiment was available. However, there was no information about which operating system and libraries were used. During the analysis of the code, we discovered impactful errors that strongly influenced the results. The most influencing one was the way how oversampling of the minority class was done. It led to overfitting and data leakage. Therefore, the reported results are overly optimistic. After we corrected the oversampling method, we carried out the same experiments as in the original paper. The performance for oversampled datasets dropped significantly and we observed that the model is not able to generalize that well anymore. This issue was also indicated by two other reproducibility studies of this paper ([2] and [5]). For datasets without oversampling, where we used exactly the same code as is the original paper, we obtained quite similar results. However, some values differed. It might be caused by a different operating system or library versions.

By doing significance testing, we could show that the conclusions of the original paper were incorrect. Another conclusion about the positive impact of oversampling was also proved to not be correct, after fixing the data leakage issue. This highlights the necessity of including significance testing when conducting machine learning experiments.

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